

Montmorillonite-catalyzed glycosylation of alcohols with glycols derived from galactose and glucose under microwave-induced reactions

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Montmorillonite K10-catalyzed glycosylation of alcohols with glycols obtained from galactose and glucose is performed efficiently using microwave irradiation with good anomeric selectivity.

Keywords: Montmorillonite K-10, glycol, ferrier rearrangement, stereoselectivity.

Introduction

Ferrier rearrangement is a crucial reaction for the preparation of 2,3-unsaturated oxygen-glycosides¹. A reaction of glycol with alcohol in the presence of an acid produces 2,3-unsaturated pyranosides by this method². Different proportions of hydrochloric acid, sulfuric acid, $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$, SnBr_4 , EtAlCl_2 are used in the Ferrier rearrangement³⁻⁶. This reaction, in general, produces a mixture of isomers. We report here a facile montmorillonite K10-catalyzed Ferrier rearrangement of numerous alcohols with glycols derived from galactose and glucose. The use of this clay as catalyst for glycosylation is not reported. Many catalysts or acidic reagents do not yield products with galactose glycol and low stereoselectivities are observed in some examples with glucose glycol⁷⁻¹⁰. We report here a simple montmorillonite-catalyzed reaction of diverse alcohols with galactose and glucose glycols under microwave irradiation.

Results and discussion

Microwave irradiation of galactose glycol **1** on reaction with alcohol **2** in the presence of montmorillonite K10 clay produced a mixture of α - and β -glycosides in good yields (**3** and **4**, Scheme 1). The reaction was extremely fast and the

Scheme 1. Montmorillonite K-10 catalyzed microwave induced glycosylation of the 3,4,6-tri-O-acetyl-D-galactal with alcohol.

Table 1

Entry	2(R)	Diastereomeric ratio ^a	Time (min)	Yield ^b (%)
		3 (α) + 4 (β)		
1	Me	3a (α) + 4a (β) [9:1]	2	90
2	Et	3b (α) + 4b (β) [9:1]	2	85
3	Bn	3c (α) + 4c (β) [8:2]	2	90
4	Cy	3d (α) + 4d (β) [7:3]	2	65
5	Cp	3e (α) + 4e (β) [7:3]	2	65
6	All	3f (α) + 4f (β) [9:1]	2	75
7	Propargyl	3g (α) + 4g (β) [9:1]	2	70

^aDiastereomeric ratio were determined by ¹H NMR of crude mixture.

^bIsolated yield after column chromatography.

axially-oriented product **3** became the predominant isomer. A similar reaction with glucose glycol **5** with alcohol **2** produced **5** and **6** (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2. Montmorillonite K-10 catalysed microwave induced glycosylation of the 3,4,6-tri-O-acetyl-D-glucal with alcohol.

Table 2

Entry	2(R)	Diastomeric ratio ^a	Time (min)	Yield ^b (%)
		6 (α) + 7 (β)		
1	Me	6a (α) + 7a (β) [9:1]	2	90
2	Et	6b (α) + 7b (β) [9:1]	2	85
3	Bn	6c (α) + 7c (β) [8:2]	2	90
4	Cy	6d (α) + 7d (β) [7:3]	2	65
5	Cp	6e (α) + 7e (β) [7:3]	2	65
6	All	6f (α) + 7f (β) [9:1]	2	75
7	Propargyl	6g (α) + 7g (β) [9:1]	2	70

^aDiastomeric ratio were determined by ¹H NMR of crude mixture.

^bIsolated yield after column chromatography.

This process induced by microwave is fascinating because highly functionalized glycoside derivatives are obtained very rapidly. Importantly, unsaturated alcohols are used successfully. Although the mechanism of this reaction is not investigated, it is assumed that the acidity of the clay is responsible for the success of this reaction. The formation of the products is explained through an allylic isomerization of the glycal to a 2,3-didehydro derivative as an intermediate. A longer reaction time with excess clay is not helpful. In fact, excess clay may also cause deglycosylation to the original alcohol and decomposed sugar residues^{12,13}.

An axial attack to the anomeric center of the allylic carbonium ion of the glycal by the -OH group is responsible for the formation of α-glycoside. An equatorial attack is responsible for β-glycoside. The product distribution indicates that the equatorial attack is not a favorable process because of the nonbonding electronic repulsive forces between the oxygen of the pyranoside ring structure and the lone pair of electrons present in the oxygen atom of the β-isomeric product (Scheme 3). The resulting carbocation reacts preferentially with alcohol from the axial side and therefore, α-glycosides become the major products. However, since the alcohols are not sterically hindered, equatorial attack is partially possible and this produces β-isomeric products.

Scheme 3. General mechanism of α-glycosylation.

A microwave reaction of diverse alcohols compounds with glycals in presence of montmorillonite K10 is developed for producing two glycosides. It is important to note that this reaction proceeds in the absence any solvent and in the presence of a solid surface. The use of montmorillonite K10 and microwave has not been investigated in a successful glycosylation reaction. In the past, success with glucose derived glycals is established with other acidic catalysts. Those reactions are time consuming and require solvents. Glycosylation with galactose glycal is extremely difficult because of the stereochemistry of the C-4 carbon center which does not participate in the anchimeric mechanistic process. On the basis of the above results, it may be possible to use this microwave method for coupling glycal derivatives with complex hydroxyl compounds to increase the solubility of the products and to use those molecules as pro-drugs.

Experimental

General procedure for the glycosylation of alcohols:

To a solution of the alcohol (1 mmol) was added tri-O-acetyl-D-glucal (1.5 mmol) followed by montmorillonite K10 (200 mg) at room temperature. The mixture was irradiated at domestic microwave oven, cooled and washed with dichloromethane. The organic part was collected and evaporated. The crude NMR spectra was taken and it showed the presence of two glycosides in unequal proportions.

Conclusions

In summary, microwave-induced reaction of hydroxy compounds with various 3-acetoxglycals in presence of iodine as a catalyst is developed for producing two separable,

Yadav *et al.*: Montmorillonite-catalyzed glycosylation of alcohols with glycols derived from galactose *etc.*

diastereomeric α -glycosides. The stereochemistry and nature of the protective groups in glycols is crucial for the success of this reaction.

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